

ADVANTAGES OF USING GREEN ENERGY

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Annotation. *This thesis highlighted the advantages of using green energy today.*

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The increase in human population on earth is increasing the demand for energy. Since the 2nd half of the 20th century, the need for electricity has been greatly increased. It affects management activities in order to reduce the consumption of fuel energy resources while maintaining the production volume in the method of energy saving management. The increase in energy consumption, the decrease and increase in the cost of energy resources, the increase in dependence on imports, the pollution of the environment create the need to achieve energy efficiency, increase the efficiency of the use of traditional energy resources, and solve the problems of developing renewable energy sources. These factors have motivated the rapid development of energy industry. The development of science and technology, the development of new methods of energy production and its transformation, the creation of new efficient equipment and technologies, the centralization of energy distribution, i.e., measures to ensure that there are no interruptions in the supply of energy sources to the population in the regions, and their correct distribution - events are being implemented.

In order to increase the energy capacity in the economy, the share of renewable energy sources should be developed rapidly. It is necessary to make systematic use of renewable energy sources, including agriculture, housing and communal areas, and solar, water, and wind energy, using the natural climatic conditions wisely. Because these resources are inexhaustible and getting the energy source is relatively cheap. If we expand our use of these renewable energy sources in the near future, the damage to the atmosphere will also be reduced somewhat.

The use of green energy sources, first of all, brings great benefits for the economy and the environment. Green energy appears to be part of the world's future, and clean energy alternatives to many of today's energy sources are being explored and implemented.

These easily replenished energy sources are not only beneficial for the environment, but also create jobs, improve the living conditions of the population, and increase their sources of income. As long as the development continues, it will be beneficial for the economic development of the country. By developing a variety of green energy solutions, we can all create a completely sustainable future for energy supply without harming the world we live in. Green energy projects have been worked on for decades and experience has been gained. For example, nowadays there is a transition from the traditional method to the non-traditional "Green Economy". That is, instead of Hydroelectric Power Stations (GES), Thermal Power Stations (IES), non-traditional sources such as solar panels, wind, water (as a result of rising sea levels) will be used. Wishing solar energy is the cleanest and most reliable source of energy for mankind today. The use of solar energy is increasing year by year. Because solar energy is an inexhaustible and environmentally friendly resource. In cooperation with the UAE company "Masdar", the construction of the first wind power plant has started in the city of Zarafshan, Navoi region. It is planned that 1.5 million households will be provided with a sufficient source of electricity through this station. In particular, in this regard, in cooperation with the "Masdar" company, work is being carried out on large-scale projects in Uzbekistan. Humanity will continue to multiply as long as it lives, and its needs for sources of electrical energy will also increase more and more. Therefore, in this regard, the use of alternative sources of energy from various sources with a low level of negative impact on the environment requires the use of energy-saving resources, techniques and technologies.

Renewable energy resources currently account for 26% of the world's electricity, but the share is expected to reach 30% by 2024, according to the IEA. The recovery followed a global slowdown in 2019 due to lower technology spending and environmental concerns.

Future renewables are predicted to increase global solar capacity to 600 gigawatts (GW) by 2024, nearly double Japan's total installed electricity capacity. Overall, renewable electricity generation is projected to grow by 1,200 GW by 2024, equal to the total electricity generation of the United States.

Based on the above, we can say that conventional energy resources are non-renewable and limited and are also responsible for climate change. Therefore, Uzbekistan can meet the energy needs of the growing population only through green energy. But green energy technology and its products are very expensive, so people are less interested in them. They can be made accessible to all by investing in technology. With the right combination of

geographic diversity and technological prowess, Uzbekistan can increase its green energy potential, thereby reducing its dependence on fossil fuel energy and handing over a greener Uzbekistan to future generations.

List of used literature:

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